

Indigeneity, Belonging and the Question of National Unity in Nigeria

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Abstract

Indigeneity as a concept is problematic; yet it has become an important factor in today's Nigerian politics. Discourses on the indigene-settler question in Nigeria have become more prominent in recent years due largely to population and agricultural expansion as well as climate change and migration. The argument about the rights and protection of indigenous peoples all over the world hinges chiefly on the notion that indigenous peoples across the globe have persistently been dominated, marginalised and dispossessed of their land and natural resources. Interestingly, the notion of indigeneity is rather complex and stretches beyond access to land natural resources. This paper demonstrates how different ethnic groups and communities in Nigeria position themselves as indigenous peoples and appropriate indigenous rights in certain localities and circumstances. The paper argues that the notion of indigeneity might also be used as a tool of empowerment by oppressed groups that require special rights.

Keywords: *indigeneity, ethnic identity, culture, land, politics.*

Introduction

The notion of indigeneity or indigenous peoples is highly controversial and political, especially in the contemporary world, where there are ongoing histories of migrations, conquests and assimilations that have created new experiences and identities. It is therefore problematic to consider indigeneity simply in terms of territorial ties or cultural connections because the conditions and experiences of being 'indigenous' in the contemporary world are 'varied, nuanced, historical, contested and always in process...'¹

As a politicised concept, indigenous peoples, may refer to different subjects depending on the context. For instance, the claim to indigeneity does not convey the same meaning in Africa as it does in North America or Oceania. Again, the Scheduled Tribes in India are not the same as the

Aboriginal peoples and Torres Strait Islander peoples of Australia. Neither do the First Nations, Inuit and Métis of Canada share commonalities in their historical experiences and cultural patterns with indigenous populations in Nigeria. Whereas indigenous peoples in Australia, Canada and the United States share common experiences of colonial domination and dispossession by the European settlers, indigenous groups in Nigeria express their rights in terms of their relationship with neighbouring ethnic groups of African descent. In fact, some scholars have even argued that the term indigenous peoples does not apply to Africa because, they believe that all Africans are indigenous to the continent and should enjoy every entitlement, including right to access to natural resources.² Based on the complexity, indigeneity should be seen in terms of the concept of 'indigenous peoples' as defined by the United Nations. The United Nations identified indigenous peoples as a distinct category and resolved that special measures should be taken to protect their rights and preserve their unique cultures and ways of life.³ Indigenous peoples are among the most disadvantaged and vulnerable groups in the world today.⁴

'Indigenous people' is a transnational term that has generated heated debates among scholars partly due to special categorisation and the issue of protection. While advocating the protection of indigenous peoples' rights, champions of indigenous identity have insisted that indigenous peoples' rights must be enshrined in United Nations human-rights legislation. Indigenous peoples around the globe may be culturally and historically heterogeneous but their problems and arguments as they relate to the protection of their rights as distinct peoples are similar. They all feel subjugated, culturally threatened and economically dispossessed by settlers or 'invading strangers'. Such fears have given rise to collaborations between indigenous peoples and non-governmental organisations such as Minority Rights Group International, the International Work Group for Indigenous Affairs, the Environmental Defence Fund, the Forest People's Movement, the Survival International, Cultural Survival, Rainforest Action Network.

The implications of indigenous rights, claims and activism as they affect national unity and development in Nigeria seem not to be clear and have not received adequate scholarly attention. This article explores the notion of indigeneity in Nigeria and how groups have engaged with the concept as a political tool. Using a select number of cases in Nigeria, the

TRIVIUM

article argues that the concept of indigeneity is problematic and has been appropriated by diverse ethnic groups for political reasons and to draw attention to their marginalisation and dispossession by more powerful groups. The paper contributes to scholarship on indigenous studies and how rights and claims in different localities contribute to irreducible ethnic conflicts in Nigeria.

The Indigene-Settler Question

Indigeneity has become a critical factor in Nigerian politics. Alpa Shah rightly described it as a political concept, stressing that ‘being indigenous is a new way of placing oneself in the world and therefore of pursuing a new type of politics, a cultural politics.’⁵ Indigeneity raises fundamental questions as to who we are and how we got to where we are. But why does the indigene-settler syndrome⁶ matter? How related and how unrelated are the ethnic groups that make up Nigeria? Who are considered indigenes and who are the settlers? Does this identity question have any implication for the unity of Nigeria? These vital questions suggest that discussions on indigeneity come with complex political agenda. Nevertheless, the indigene-settler dichotomy is largely a product of population expansion and waves of mass migration that have changed the landscape of human population on the African continent. People have migrated and continue to migrate from their places of origin to places where they displace or mix up with other groups that had settled before their arrival. Most of the human migrations in Nigeria and the rest of Africa were as a result of the spread of agriculture. As the Sahara Desert expanded due to climate change, farming and herding also spread, especially in the West African sub-region. Continuous migrations have, therefore, made it difficult to tell how the ancestral populations of modern humans in Africa were formed. Although Africa appears to be extraordinary in human diversity, a recent study of genes across the globe shows that all modern humans in Africa are interrelated.⁷ West Africa in particular has the largest population of people whose ancestors are interrelated.

Sometimes, the inhabitants of a particular area may not be the actual descendants of the first group of people to settle in that geographical location. People freely co-existed in Africa, and there were opportunities for integration and interbreeding as the population grew until the European colonial conquest. Owing to a mixture that might have occurred in the distant past, some groups find it difficult to determine their ancestry.

Interestingly, the ability of a group of people to establish the antiquity of the occupation of their ancestors in a particular region is a major criterion for determining their indigeneity and their ability to position themselves for empowerment.

Indigenous peoples can be described as the first set of people to settle in a particular geographical location with their cultures and traditions established and tied to that same territory where they have occupied for a long period of time. The United Nations described them as the ‘inheritors and practitioners of unique cultures and ways of relating to people and the environment’.⁸ Although indigenes are generally regarded as the first inhabitants of an area, a group of people may also conquer or displace an existing weaker group to establish itself as the natives of an area. Whereas such early inhabitants are considered indigenes or natives of the land, successive groups that later arrived and settled are regarded as settlers or strangers. The categorization of groups as indigenes and settlers is often tied to rights, and such a categorization, to a large extent, determines who gets some entitlements in a community. In most cases, people claim to be indigenes of a place based on the length of time they have resided in that area, but indigeneity is a collective claim that is usually based on descent or somebody’s ancestral link to a particular territory. Thus, indigeneity or nativity is not based on mere residence but by a group’s descent and close attachment to an ancestral territory and the natural resources in that area.

Groups who claim indigeneship or nativity of a place regard themselves as autochthones (‘sons of the soil’) and hold strongly to the view that as indigenes, they have exclusive rights to land resource by reason of their link to blood and soil. The idea of indigeneity has also manifested in other aspects of the community life, including politics.⁹ Shah described it as an ‘important tool of articulation for empowerment’,¹⁰ and groups use it to defend their positions. In many communities, indigenous groups express more sense of entitlement in decision-making and right to resources. In such places, right to resources is based on ‘indigeneship’ and ‘settlership’ status. This partly explains the emotional claim or obsession with indigenous identity. This social division, which is exemplified by the Igbo¹¹ concepts, *Amala* (natives or indigenes) and *Ndi-obia/Mbia-mbia* (strangers or settlers) have also invaded the academic community. It is common knowledge in Nigeria today that indigenous groups now insist that their sons or daughters should be appointed to head academic

TRIVIUM

institutions located in their states as against the tradition of selecting the best candidate based on qualifications. Indigenous groups may have their reasons, but such agitations demonstrate the extent to which the notion of indigeneity has localised the essence of university.

The notion of indigeneity leads to struggle and sometimes violent confrontations because groups use it to exclude others from benefitting from social, economic and political entitlements in a community. Settler groups in different communities often challenge the 'settler label'. They argue that their long term residency and active participation in a community should qualify them to be recognised as indigenes. Unfortunately, the length of time one has lived in a particular place does not entitle the person to become an indigene. But how do we explain the fact that the Jukun in Wukari still see their Tiv neighbours as settlers despite the fact that the Tiv have occupied the same area since the nineteenth century? While the status of settlers in postcolonial societies in Nigeria may remain constant, one wonders how the so-called indigenous activists think they can make substantial progress with their strong emphasis on localism in a globalising world.

Although some consider the concept of indigeneity as a social construct, it sometimes serves the purpose of protecting a particular group from extreme discrimination, dispossession and marginalisation or even being wiped out of existence. Until the colonial conquest, Africa was largely characterised by flexibility of identity, and it was easy for migrants to transform their identity from settlers to indigenes without challenges, provided such settlers were committed to identify with and be integrated into the host community.¹² But since the British conquest and their *Pax Britannica* (British Peace), the process of 'indigenising' or assimilating settlers has become very difficult. The British colonial policy in Nigeria, in its self-serving purpose of divide and rule, destroyed the process of flexible transformation from settler to indigene by emphasising the use of the label, 'strangers' in a country of one's birth. In Northern Nigerian towns, southern Nigerians were forced to live outside the walls in *Sabon Gari*¹³ (strangers' quarters) during the colonial rule. This policy underpinned ethnic distinction and a deeply structured inequality. That was how identities changed in relation to colonialism through history. The discriminatory policy of keeping southern 'immigrants' at *Sabon Gari* and the official recognition of such social arrangement created 'foreigners' within a group

of citizens of the same country. It prevented Southern Nigerians from being integrated into the host communities, and with time, the excluded ethnic groups became ethnically conscious and began to group themselves together as lineages and ethnic unions. The formation of lineage and ethnic unions was a way of ensuring security for their members as well as fighting social alienation. With time, the champions of the ethnic unions became the leaders of the political parties that fought for the independence of Nigeria. During the struggle for independence, the nationalists began to see themselves as ethnic entrepreneurs or regional politicians, and the political parties they formed later emerged as champions of ethnic and regional interests. This partly explains how Nigeria slipped into the tar pit of ethnic politics.

Indeed, the colonial authorities supported the indigene-settler dichotomy when they maintained that the north should be left for the northerners. This policy did not only obstruct the spread of Western education but also emphasised the ethnic and religious differences among the groups that make up the political unit called Nigeria. They claimed to have created a united country but adopted different administrative policies that further hyphenated religious, cultural and ethnic differences of the ethnic groups. The consequence of the British colonial policy in Nigeria is that Northerners continue to complain about being educationally disadvantaged, despite the fact that they have ruled the country for many years. The British regard their colonial rule in Nigeria as their finest achievement in Africa, but the union they formed was in fact a political laboratory to test their ideas. The British colonial rule in Nigeria was a phenomenal upheaval, and the huge impact is still being felt. One of the consequences of their political experiment is that the constitutions they introduced left the country permanently divided. The quota system with its inherent injustice is a very good example. *Boko Haram* could not have emerged if Northerners had been reasonably exposed to the opportunities offered by Western education. Neither the colonial authorities provided adequate educational facilities in the North, nor did they allow the missionaries to do so. It is obvious that the major interest of British in Nigeria was economic, and to achieve that, they made policies that helped to destroy the traditional institutions while pretending to be preserving them. The colonial experiment in Nigeria has been facing a serious threat since its inception because it was ill-adapted to the ethnic and religious realities in the country. The amalgamation of the Southern and Northern

TRIVIUM

Protectorates in 1914 and the colonial constitutions succeeded in creating a state with strong ethnic and religious identities and these identities have turned out to be the strong triggers of conflicts in postcolonial Nigeria.

Some Cases of Indigene-Settler Conflict in Nigeria

The Ife-Modakeke conflict in Osun State is perhaps the earliest and longest intra-ethnic conflict in Nigeria. The conflict which has lasted over a century is hinged on the indigene-settler question. Ile-Ife is no doubt the ancestral political, cultural and spiritual headquarters of the Yoruba. As cradle of the Yoruba ethnic group, every other group that settled later in Ife is regarded as a 'tenant or stranger.' The Modakeke (tenants/settlers) settled in Ile-Ife as refugees after the fall of the Old Oyo Empire in the early 1800s.¹⁴ Hence, the relationship between Ife and Modakeke was originally on the landlord-tenant basis. Soon after the settlement of the Modakeke in Ife, conflicts began, leading to the resettlement of the Modakeke by Ooni Abegunle Abeweila. The Ife-Modakeke conflict started around 1835 as a result of identity recognition, inheritance protection and property rights.¹⁵ The Modakeke strongly believe in their distinct identity and did not want to be assimilated into the Ife society. They also wanted payments for land to Ife to be stopped.¹⁶ The people of Ife, like the biblical Egyptians, were opposed to the separation and autonomy of Modakeke primarily due to the loss of economic benefits they derived from having the Modakeke as part and parcel of Ife.¹⁷ For over a century, identity (indigene/settler status), land and rent have been triggers of conflicts between the two Yoruba groups. The consequences of such conflicts have been the loss of lives and property, and the disintegration of families.¹⁸

The Zango-Kataf crisis which occurred in February and May, 1992, is one of the most violent conflicts arising from indigene-settler syndrome in postcolonial Nigeria. The primary cause of the conflict is the struggle over land. In Zango-Kataf, the Atyap, who are predominantly Christians, constitute the major indigenous group and they are mainly farmers. The Hausa-Fulani herders who are regarded as 'migrants' or settlers do not have easy access to green grass to feed their cattle, and they have always wanted grazing reserves in the land belonging to the indigenous peoples of Zango-Kataf in Southern Kaduna.¹⁹ An attempt to expropriate land belonging to the indigenous groups led to conflicts between the indigenous peoples and the Hausa-Fulani herders. Although struggle over land had been a perennial issue in the relations between the Hausa and the indigenous peoples, the

1992 conflict was triggered by the attempt to relocate the Zango-Kataf market to a new place that was considered more spacious. Most of the Hausa-Fulani traders were strongly opposed to such relocation because of its location. The market crisis resulted in the loss of lives on both sides of the conflict, and property, crops and farmland were destroyed, resulting in famine and suffering in Southern Kaduna.

The indigenous peoples who had been marginalised under the British colonial rule suffered more casualties since the Hausa-Fulani group was better armed. The Zango-Kataf crisis was complicated by the fact that the Fulani hired mercenaries from Niger, Chad, Cameroon, Mali and Senegal who helped them to subdue the indigenes.²⁰ The indigenous people who tried to resist the Fulani encroachment were either killed or chased out of their area. Until the conflict, the Hausa-Fulani and the indigenes had coexisted, but since the 1992, Zango-Kataf has been divided along ethnic and religious lines. Although the situation appeared to have been brought under control, there have been incessant clashes between the natives and the Hausa-Fulani herders in Southern Kaduna. The conflict which was originally about access to land resource assumed a more religious dimension with the introduction of sharia in Northern Nigeria in 2000. One of the most recent clashes which claimed over eight hundred members of the indigenous people has also been described as genocide.

The Tiv-Jukun conflict is one of the major inter-ethnic conflicts in Nigeria and it has lingered since 1959. The Tiv and the Jukun are both found in Taraba and Benue States. Land has been one of the major issues that precipitate conflicts between the Tiv and the Jukun.²¹ The Jukun of Taraba claim to be the indigenes of Wukari and argue that the Tiv are settlers and do not own the land they occupy. The Tiv on the other hand challenge the settler status apportioned to them by the Jukun on the ground that they too have been living in Wukari for a very long time and deserve equal rights to land and political positions as citizens.²² These claims by the two ethnic groups have affected their relations and generated violent conflicts in Wukari. The interesting thing in the Tiv-Jukun relations is that the Tiv in Wukari are larger in number and they take advantage of their number in making decisions in politics. The Jukun have always tried to resist the number game in politics by insisting on indigeneity as the basis of political appointments. Consequently, the two ethnic groups have been in constant struggle over land resources and political positions, and this has

TRIVIUM

posed a big constitutional question on citizenship rights in Nigeria.

The conflict between the Hausa-Fulani (categorised as settlers / Muslims) and the Berom, Anaguta, Afisare (regarded as the indigenes/Christians/traditionalists)²³ in Jos has posed a great challenge to national peace and security. The conflict centres largely on the struggle over land and chieftaincy. The inhabitants of Jos are mainly farmers who depend on land as means of livelihood. With the increase in population and agricultural expansion in recent years, land has become a very important asset in Jos. Indigenous farmers and Hausa-Fulani herders need land to sustain their economic activities and have been involved in perennial conflicts with each other. However, the crisis in Jos cannot be explained by materialism alone. It is also about social survival of the indigenous group whose traditional institutions are being threatened by the Hausa-Fulani demand for the establishment of their own chieftaincy. The indigenous peoples of Jos see the Hausa-Fulani agitation for the recognition of their own political institution as a threat to their social existence. The politics of belonging is not just limited to chieftaincy and struggle for land resource, it has also manifested in the political sphere with the result that participation in government is often determined by one's status either as an indigene or a settler.

The willingness to identify with and be integrated into the host community is another major issue in the Jos conflict. For the period the Hausa-Fulani group have settled in Jos, they have refused to adapt and integrate into the Jos Plateau society. For instance, the Hausa-Fulani would marry from the indigenous community but would not allow a member of the host community to marry their own daughters. The Hausa-Fulani also do not recognise the culture, religion and traditional institutions of their host community.²⁴ Perhaps they believe they have little or nothing in common with the indigenous peoples. The indigene-settler division in Jos is complicated by the differences in the ethnicity and religions of the groups that are involved in the conflict. These differences explain why it has been difficult to bring peace between the two groups.

The Ezza-Ezillo intra-communal crisis in Ebonyi State is another interesting case of indigene-settler struggle. The Ezillo who occupy Ishielu Local Government Area of Ebonyi State are regarded as the indigenous group in Ezillo whereas the Ezza-Ezillo are seen as settlers. The Ezza-Ezillo settled at Ezillo in the early 1930s after assisting Ezillo people to

wage a war against their Ngbo neighbours in Ohaukwu Local Government Area, who were encroaching into their territory. At the end of the war, elders of Ezillo gave a piece of land at Eguechara to Ezza-Ezillo people in recognition of their assistance in the war against the Ngbo. Since then, the Ezza-Ezillo and Ezillo people coexisted peacefully until the Ezza-Ezillo gradually expanded in population and began to settle in other parts of Ezillo.

The Ezillo noticed the encroachment and insisted on the relocation of the Ezza-Ezillo to Eguechara where they were given by the elders of Ezillo. The struggle over land continued until the matter was taken to the Abakaliki colonial court in 1959 and was ruled in favour of the Ezillo.²⁵ Ezza-Ezillo people appealed to the Colonial District Officer in Abakaliki, O. P. Gunning but lost again. Yet, they refused to relocate. The immediate cause of the Ezza-Ezillo and Ezillo conflict which started on May 10, 2008, at Ishimkpuma market square was as a result of struggle over where to locate a commercial phone booth. This struggle over land in Ezillo resulted in the destruction of property and lives. The most unfortunate part of the conflict is that some innocent citizens who were travelling through the Abakaliki-Enugu highway were killed by the warring parties. A panel of enquiry was set up by the Ebonyi State Government to review the matter. On October 2, 2008, the Ebonyi State Government released a white paper directing the Ezza to move back to Eguechara based on their status as settlers in Ezillo.²⁶ The Ezza people protested against the decision of the government, arguing that they could not abandon their houses and cash crops. Despite the efforts of the Ebonyi State government to mediate in the crisis, the conflict appears to remain unresolved. Although the cause of the conflict is easily linked to the phone booth incident, the underlying cause of the conflict is primarily the indigene-settler dichotomy.

Indigeneity and the Citizenship Question

The indigene-settler question has transformed the way we think and how we relate with one another in a community. There may be nothing wrong with claiming collective rights based on the indigeneity of a group in a locality, but such claims in Nigeria have often conflicted with individual rights of citizens. The obsession with belonging and the social division it creates, has unfortunately, made it difficult for Nigeria to achieve national integration. Belonging is not essentially a problem but what people do with

TRIVIUM

it is one. Sometimes, groups claim indigeneity in order to establish control and extinguish other interests. Indigeneity claims should ideally protect the indigenous groups who are considered marginalised, but the political elite sometimes manipulate the notion by using it as a mobilising platform to secure personal gains. The indigene-settler dichotomy in Nigeria produces superior-inferior relationship or social inequality, especially when it comes to resource distribution and political participation; and this form of relationship has raised some unsettled questions on citizenship rights in Nigeria. How can an individual commit total loyalty to the nation when the national constitution itself does not adequately provide for individual rights? The notion of indigeneity in Nigeria clearly challenges national citizenship and undermines the idea of national unity and equality of all citizens.²⁷ Indigenous groups exist in different parts of the world – the United States of America, Canada, Australia and New Zealand, but there is a legal framework that reduces the tension and to a large extent, guarantees the equality to every citizen in those countries. But the Nigerian concept of ‘indigeneship’ is different and has been overstretched in the name of federal character and quota system.

The issue is that those who fought for the independence of Nigeria had no vision about the kind of country they wanted to build. Even after independence, the leaders were not yet convinced about the efficacy of the colonially constructed federation. Why should a citizen of Nigeria be regarded as a stranger or foreigner in his or her country? The reason is that the Nigerian concept of citizenship is tied to indigeneity and ethnic loyalty. In fact, Nigeria has more ethnic and religious citizens than national citizens. Nigerians are first of all loyal to their villages, their ethnic and religious groups before their country. Given that loyalty is multilayered, the position of the nation is relegated to the background. How can a society with this kind of structure support national unity and development? If a citizen of Nigeria who pays taxes accordingly can be considered a stranger in his own country just because he moved out of his natal habitat, it means that a citizen of another country has little or no chance of being integrated into the Nigerian society. This sense of localism makes it difficult for Nigeria to be integrated into the global village.

Unfortunately, there is no viable constitutional framework to deal with the challenges of indigene-settler cleavage in Nigeria. The Nigerian constitution is so disarticulated that people who migrated out of their

ancestral homes to neighbouring states are regarded as settlers and “foreigners” in their country of birth. The ‘deportation’ of Igbos, believed to be beggars in Lagos State exemplifies the notions of indigene and foreigner in Nigeria. The 1999 Constitution which makes anybody whose grandparent was a member of a community indigenous to that state makes it difficult for new migrants from neighbouring states to be absorbed as members of that state with full rights. In other words, you have to belong to an indigenous community before you can claim citizenship. This is a constitutional crisis, and the danger is that national integration and unity will remain elusive in Nigeria until the issue is addressed through a constitutional review.

The indigene-settler confrontation has affected political, economic and social relations among different groups in Nigeria, and the end is not in sight. It has also engendered social injustice and minimised popular participation in governance. The idea of meritocracy continues to face serious erosion in the face of indigeneity claims. Being an indigene of a particular group gives one an advantage over another in federal appointments regardless of educational qualifications. How does one construct a democratic and inclusive society in the face of indigene-settler cleavage in Nigeria? The social exclusion created by the politics of belonging has produced a social tension which has in turn put communities on the verge of constant violent confrontation.

Conclusion

The notions of indigeneship and settlership have remained a serious threat to national peace, unity and development. It has negatively affected intergroup relations and precipitated a number of conflicts across the country. The indigenous groups often feel threatened by the settler or migrant groups, who not only compete for economic and political survival but try to impose their cultural values on the indigenous groups. Indigeneity claim is not only about land; it is also about history, culture and the social survival of the indigenous communities. Although the concept of indigeneity challenges the imperial assumptions of *terra nullius* (nobody’s land)²⁸ which was used to rationalise the European conquest and acquisition of territories in different parts of the world, it is at the same time in conflict with the notion of citizenship. It has created social hierarchies and inequalities that have not only generated tensions but have also eroded important values such as meritocracy and democracy. The popular slogan,

TRIVIUM

‘unity in diversity’ is no longer relevant. Nigeria is on the precipice and is progressively collapsing under the heavy weight of ethnicity and religious fundamentalism.

Implications for History

There is no doubt that the indigeneship-settlership question in Nigeria has placed migration in the limelight. It has also led to a renewed interest in local history and the rights of antecedent inhabitants. There are many cases in the court of law pertaining to historical occupancy, root title to land and possessory rights. Every group is interested in its past because people use history to establish the antiquity of their ancestry and to show who they are in a community. A group that is able to establish its descent and historical occupancy in a territory uses such facts to legitimise its nativity and power to exclude others in resource distribution. History, therefore, is considered a powerful tool in the settler-indigene struggle. Indigenous groups’ attempts at establishing exclusive right to natural resource exploitation and other benefits in society may be justified, but this is often done without minding the implication on perceived settlers who share the same geographical space with the so-called indigenes. Using history to create a division between the settler and indigene has led to intense construction and reconstruction of migration histories of different groups in order to establish legal status and refute those of the rivals. Oral tradition at this point becomes indispensable. Groups sometimes construct unverifiable myths to justify their claims or even attempt to uproot existing native title.

The claims and counterclaims about the indigeneship of groups have also repositioned the colonial archives as definitive sources of information about the past. The good thing about the struggle is that people now go to national archives to dig out records that were documented by colonial officials, anthropologists and missionaries. Such records which had existed for decades without being touched have helped in settling the indigene-settler conflicts in some places. Such visits to archives have not only reawakened people’s interest in record keeping but also generated revenue for the national archives whose official stamps are needed for such records to be admitted in the courts of law. Nevertheless, learning about the deep past of our ancestors through the archives can be problematic. It does not provide all the necessary details that may be needed to settle conflicts that are related to ancestry and settlement. Given the lingering cases in the

court of law, people may at some point, resort to using DNA to determine ancestry or indigeneship of groups in a particular area. But this certainly will not solve the complex problem of indigeneship and settlersip in Nigeria.

Endnotes:

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- ² Michaela Pelican, 'Complexities of Indigeneity and Autochthony: An African Example' *American Ethnologist*, 36.1 (2009): 52-65, 52-53.
- ³ See Douglas Sanders, 'The UN Working Group on Indigenous Populations' *Human Rights Quarterly* 11.3(1989): 406-433.
- ⁴ 'Indigenous Peoples at the United Nations' <https://www.un.org/development/desa/indigenouspeoples/about-us.html>. Accessed 15.01.2021.
- ⁵ Alpa Shah, *In the Shadows of the State: Indigenous Politics, Environmentalism and Insurgency in Jharkhand, India* (Durham: Duke University Press, 2010), p. 24.
- ⁶ The indigene-settler syndrome can be described as an identity issue that is characterized by a persistent attitude of claiming ancestry or group right to land in a particular geographical area based on history of settlement. Such claims to land and natural resources in Nigeria have led to violent conflicts between groups.
- ⁷ David Reich, *Who We Are and How We Got Here: Ancient DNA and the New Science of the Human Past* (New Delhi: Oxford University Press, 2018), p. 213.
- ⁸ 'Indigenous Peoples at the United Nations.'
- ⁹ Rogers TabeEgbeOrock, 'The indigene-Settler Divide, Modernisation and the Land Question: Indications for Social Disorder in Cameroon,' *Nordic Journal of African Studies*, 14.1 (2005) : 68-78, 69.
- ¹⁰ Shah, *In the Shadows of the State*, p. 24.
- ¹¹ Igbo is one of the major ethnic groups in Nigeria.
- ¹² Umar Habila Dadem Danfulani, 'The Jos Conference and the Indigene-Settler Question in Nigerian Politics' (Draft), ASC, Leiden/University of Jos, 2006, p. 15. <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/9b2e/4dcc6a36404c39882ce84675ec5a60ff052a.pdf>. Accessed 17.12.2018.
- ¹³ *Sabon Gari* is a Hausa expression for strangers' quarters. For more information, see Michael Crowder, *The History of Nigeria* (London: Faber and Faber, 1978), p. 228.
- ¹⁴ Bukola Adeyemi Oyeniyi, 'Greed-Grievance Debate and the Ife-Modakeke Conflict' *Social History* 35.3 (2010): 308-329, 308.

TRIVIUM

- ¹⁵ See Olakunle Michael Folami and Taiwo Akanbi Olaiya, 'Gender, Storytelling and Peace Construction in a Divided Society: A Case Study of the Ife-Modakeke Crisis,' *Cogent Social Sciences* 2 (2016): 1-19, 3. <https://www.cogentoa.com/article/10.1080/23311886.2016.1159015.pdf>. Accessed 07.01.2019.
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- ¹⁹ Favour ChukwuemekaUroko, 'Readdressing the Ethno-Religious Conflict in Southern Kaduna, Nigeria, in the Light of Abraham Lot Narrative (Genesis 13: 1-18)' *UJAH: Unizik Journal of Arts and Humanities* 19.2 (2018) : 25-43, 32-33.
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